

Innovative Experiences in Engineering Education: Leveraging Continuous Improvement in the Automotive Industry

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Abstract

This study explores the effective implementation of Problem-Based Learning (PBL) and the Kaizen methodology within the automotive industry, specifically through the development of a wheeled trolley for moving heavy parts. PBL enabled engineering students to apply theoretical knowledge to practical, real-world challenges, fostering innovation and continuous improvement. The Kaizen methodology facilitated a collaborative approach to identify areas for enhancement, devise effective solutions, and assess their impact on production line efficiency and productivity. The introduction of the trolley significantly reduced operational steps, increased productivity, and improved ergonomic conditions, demonstrating the operational and safety benefits. This experience underscores the critical role of innovative practices in engineering education, preparing future professionals to tackle the evolving challenges of the industry.

Keywords: Problem-Based Learning; Kaizen; Teaching of Automotive Engineering; Continuous Improvement.

1 Introduction

In the automotive industry, where innovation is a constant and the demand for technical and creative skills is essential, engineering education transcends the traditional confines of the classroom. Problem-Based Learning (PBL) emerges as a pioneering methodology, empowering future professionals not only with theoretical knowledge, but with the ability to face real challenges in the sector. (Ribeiro, 2008)

In this case study, PBL is adopted as a catalyst for continuous improvement in the automotive industry, aligning with the essence of Kaizen, a Japanese philosophy that advocates continuous improvement. The focus is to create a Dolly Wheel, a crucial piece of equipment in the optimization of the assembly line. By integrating PBL into engineering education, it not only promotes the development of practical skills but also creates a strong bridge between theory and practice. (Araújo, 2011).

PBL not only enriches the educational journey of students but also fosters the growth of teachers by encouraging collaboration and knowledge exchange in a dynamic environment. Recognized for its effectiveness in several areas of knowledge, PBL plays a key role in preparing the engineers of the future for the complex and emerging challenges of the automotive industry. The integration of active methodologies, such as PBL, in higher education has been seen as fundamental for the development of students' critical thinking (Rezende and Silva-Salse, 2021)

As the automotive industry moves towards sustainable mobility (Lara and Marx, 2015), the application of PBL in engineering education becomes even more crucial. Innovative experiences in teaching not only empower students with practical skills, but also stimulate creativity and stimulate complex problem-solving, preparing them to thrive in a context of constant change in professional life.

2 Method

The present work is characterized as a case study applied to an automaker based in Curitiba that stands out in the manufacture and assembly of heavy vehicles. This study was carried out in two distinct phases: an extensive review of the literature related to the topics in question and a field investigation in the process/area: Preparation and sequencing of axles of heavy vehicles. The last stage was carried out through case studies, a method considered appropriate by Yin (2005) to explore contemporary phenomena in their real contexts, using various sources of evidence, such as interviews, direct observations and document analysis. The author highlights the ability to use multiple sources of evidence as one of the distinguishing features of case study-based research.

2.1 Case Study: Stages of PBL

After the evaluation and approval of the wheeled trolley, the project is considered to be successfully completed. Presentation of Results: The team presents the results of the project, including the benefits and impacts on the productivity and safety of the production line. A final review of the project is conducted, documenting the results achieved, lessons learned, and recommendations for future improvements.

Table 1. Stages of the Case Study

Stage	Description
1	The employee, a student of production engineering, identifies a problem on the production line: difficulty in moving heavy parts. This can include data analysis, workplace observations, and feedback from colleagues.
2	The improvement proposal is registered in the factory's internal program for analysis and approval. At this stage, the employee formally presents the proposal, describing the problem, possible solutions, and expected benefits.
3	The project team initiates the Kaizen process by documenting the current state of the process with flowcharts or visual representations. Detailed reviews of the existing process are conducted to identify areas of improvement and understand the underlying causes of the problem.
4	The team proposes an innovative solution, such as the development of a prototype wheeled trolley to facilitate the movement of the parts. The proposed solutions are discussed and evaluated for technical and economic feasibility.
5	The team seeks authorization from the logistics engineering department for the implementation of the solution. Formal approval from the logistics team is requested, ensuring that the proposed solution is compatible with existing processes and operational requirements.
6	The team prepares a budget and submits it to the cost center for an evaluation of the benefit/cost ratio. Approval guarantees the start of production. A detailed budget is prepared, including the costs of materials, labor, and any other resources required for the implementation of the solution.
7	The team forwards the order to the Kaizen workshop, which specializes in the manufacture of the wheeled trolley. After the budget is approved, the order is sent to the workshop responsible for manufacturing the wheeled trolley, where the production process will be started according to the specifications provided by the project team.
8	The wheeled trolley is manufactured and delivered to the applicant for testing and evaluation. The Kaizen workshop manufactures the trolley according to the specifications provided by the project team and delivers it to the applicant for testing and evaluation under real working conditions.
9	The applicant tests the wheeled trolley in a variety of situations to verify its feasibility and efficiency. Comprehensive testing is performed to ensure that the cart meets operational requirements and provides significant improvements over the previous method of moving parts.
10	After the evaluation and approval of the wheeled trolley, the project is considered to be successfully completed. Presentation of Results: The team presents the results of the project, including the benefits and impacts on the productivity and safety of the production line. A final review of the project is conducted, documenting the results achieved, lessons learned, and recommendations for future improvements.

3 Findings

After the demand was identified, the problem was promptly registered in the company's continuous improvement system. This record marks the beginning of the improvement process, giving formality and priority to the identified theme. The development of Kaizen, a method aimed at continuous improvement, begins. This process involves the collaboration of multidisciplinary teams, which focus on the detailed analysis of the problem, the identification of its root causes, and the proposition of effective solutions to mitigate the excess movement during the sequencing and preparation of the axes in the production line.

To corroborate and deepen the analysis of the waste generated by unnecessary movements, a spaghetti chart was prepared, which is of great importance for reducing the movement time and the need for movement (Coutinho, 2020). This graphic was created with the objective of visually mapping the flow of movement of the elements used during the process of sequencing and preparation of the axes in the production line, as shown in figure 1.

Figure 1. Spaghetti Chart Process Mapping Image

This analysis was based on a three-vehicle manufacturing round, in which the operator's steps were recorded through a counting application, totaling 899 steps, between sequencing and axle preparation. This visual representation provided valuable insights by identifying the points with the most unnecessary movement, highlighting critical areas that needed intervention to improve the process. This step was essential to identify potential solutions and consolidate the need to implement substantial improvements in the operational flow.

Subsequently, the Ishikawa Diagram was elaborated, as illustrated in Figure 2. Also known as a Cause and Effect Diagram or Fishbone Diagram, this analytical framework establishes a relationship between the effects and causes of a process. It is recognized that each effect has specific origins, allowing the inclusion of other causes that may arise during the development of the process (Rodrigues, 2006).

TOOLS FOR ROOT CAUSE ANALYSIS

Figure 2. Ishikawa diagram reducing excess movement

The shaft must be unpacked, sequenced and with the discs assembled, before being sent to the assembly line.

Table 2. Potential Causes

CAUSES	POTENTIAL CAUSES		
	WHY 1	WHY 2	WHY 3
Reduction of excess movement in shaft preparation and sequencing.	There is an excess of movement when preparing the shaft;	You need to transport several components to perform the same operation;	The shaft must be unpacked, sequenced and with the discs assembled, before being sent to the assembly line.

According to Jucan (2005), the effort to identify the root cause of a problem is not an easy process, it depends on the experience of the team, in this context two main points are identified: first, the complexity of the operation due to the need for several procedures, tools and devices; second, the ample space required to move the axles with the Jeep, resulting in a significant operational displacement. Excessive complexity in performing tasks can lead to inefficiencies, while the extension of the environment contributes to wasted time and resources.

After a thorough analysis of the spaghetti chart and the Ishikawa Diagram by the Kaizen team, the initial objectives and goals outlined were shown to be guidelines for concrete actions. After brainstorming, the group intends to develop a multifunctional cart, capable of accommodating and transporting all the items, tools and devices essential for carrying out the operation, aiming at the optimization and practicality of the process. In addition, the team is committed to drastically reducing the number of steps involved in the current operation, aiming for a decrease of more than 30%.

This goal aims to simplify and improve workflow efficiency, providing greater agility and reducing potential errors. At the same time, another crucial objective is to considerably minimize the risk of accidents related to falling devices or injuries caused by overloading, aiming at a safer and more secure working environment for employees involved in the operational process. These goals reflect not only the pursuit of operational improvements, but also the commitment to safety and continuous improvement of procedures within the context of Kaizen.

An effort to find a solution was immediately initiated. Initially, a rudimentary sketch of a prototype was prepared to meet the identified operational demands. This prototype was conceived as an initial response to

the emerging needs of the operation, serving as a basis for potential improvements in the process of preparing and sequencing the axes on the production line, as illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Sketch of the Cart Prototype

The dolly wheel is a versatile and adaptable solution, with a removable and recyclable structure. Its rugged tubular frame provides protection for parts and operators, resisting water, dust, corrosion, and solvents for durability in a variety of conditions. Made with 2mm aluminum tubes and reinforced joints, your 100mm Graphit wheel options ensure efficient mobility. Its divisions can be customized with nylon or PVC to meet specific needs, facilitating the efficient movement of loads and reducing the effort of operators, improving transport capacity and minimizing unnecessary movements – Does Not Add Value to Product (NAV).

Continuing the phases, the next step is the involvement of Logistics Engineering. Their team plays a central role in obtaining authorization to start production, carefully analyzing the logistical requirements for transportation, storage, and distribution of materials and components essential to manufacturing.

Release by the Cost Center involves analyzing the submitted budget, assessing whether the expected benefits outweigh the costs associated with the project. If the benefit/cost ratio is favorable, the start of production is authorized, ensuring that investments are in line with the expected returns for the organization.

In the Kaizen Workshop stage, logistics engineering is directed to an environment specialized in manufacturing and process improvement. Upon arrival at the workshop, the logistics team enters the order into the production queue, initiating the implementation process. This workshop, recognized for its focus on continuous improvements and efficiency in manufacturing, represents a strategic environment where demands are addressed and integrated into the production flow, aiming to improve logistics procedures and manufacturing practices.

In this Production and Delivery phase, the trolley is meticulously manufactured according to the specifications of the order, going through all the stages from production to assembly and finishing, using the necessary materials. Upon completion, the cart is delivered to the requester, meeting the established requirements and ready to meet the identified operational demands, as illustrated in figure 4.

Figure 4. Finished Dolly Wheel

In the Feasibility Testing stage, the candidate subjects the cart to tests to evaluate its effectiveness. The results reveal a significant reduction in the number of steps taken by the operator, decreasing from 899 to 219 after the cart was deployed. In addition, there was a notable increase in productivity: before, 36 vehicles were manufactured per operator/shift, while after the use of the trailer, this number rose to 41 vehicles, without the need for additional costs with hiring labor to meet demand, evidencing the positive impacts on efficiency and production flow.

In the feasibility testing process, considerable savings in physical and muscular strength were verified. This reduction contributed to reducing operator wear, avoiding physical overloads that could result in damage to health, in addition to providing a more ergonomically appropriate and safer work environment. These results reinforce the benefits of the trolley not only in terms of operational efficiency, but also in preserving the health and well-being of workers.

4 Conclusion

The study "Innovative Experiences in Engineering Education: Leveraging Continuous Improvement in the Automotive Industry" highlights the effectiveness of Problem-Based Learning (PBL) as the main methodology for the development of practical and analytical skills in engineering students. Through a case study in a heavy vehicle manufacturer, it was demonstrated that PBL, by enabling students to face real challenges and promote creative solutions, is fundamental for the training of engineers prepared for the market. The Kaizen methodology was used as a complementary support tool to PBL, facilitating the identification of opportunities for improvement and the development of effective solutions. This combination has resulted in significant improvements to the production line, including reducing the number of operational steps, increasing productivity, and improving the ergonomic conditions of workers.

If the Kaizen methodology had not been adopted as a complement to PBL, the learning outcomes would still have been significant, but with some limitations. The absence of Kaizen could reduce the emphasis on continuous and systematic collaboration, which is essential for developing communication and cooperation skills. Without the Kaizen philosophy, students might not experience the iterative practice of continuous improvement, which is crucial for efficiency and innovation in the automotive industry. In addition, students could develop solutions that are less applicable to the real world, limiting the relevance of their skills in the industrial context. Detailed analysis tools, such as the Ishikawa Diagram and spaghetti charts, could not be used, resulting in a less deep understanding of problems and their root causes.

Therefore, even without the Kaizen methodology, PBL would still provide robust and practical training, preparing students to face real challenges. However, the combination of PBL with Kaizen further enriches learning by encouraging a culture of continuous improvement and innovation. The experience documented in the study serves as an inspiring model for the integration of innovative practices in engineering education, demonstrating that the combination of PBL and Kaizen is highly beneficial for the training of qualified professionals who are adaptable to the constant challenges of the market.

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